

Job Satisfaction Trends in a Trinidad and Tobago Sample of Self-Employed and Paid Workers

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Abstract

Job satisfaction among paid employees has been found to correlate positively with employee commitment and retention and, subsequently, organizational productivity and effectiveness. From a human development perspective, work satisfaction is also crucial to happiness and overall wellbeing. Within a broader overarching study of Quality of Life (QoL), the authors did an evaluation of work satisfaction as experienced by both entrepreneurs and paid employees in Trinidad and Tobago. By contrasting the experiences of individuals engaged in these types of employment, we uncovered some insightful workplace trends and gained a deeper understanding of the needs of paid employees. Several scales were developed, using an inductive approach, to capture determinants of current QoL, factors which influenced choice of work, current work challenges, and future concerns for the individuals sampled. Information from some of these scales was incorporated, via a series of statistically validated steps, into a multivariate index which could be used to measure QoL, not just among the general population of Trinidad and Tobago but, arguably, worldwide. One of the key scales used to develop the index is a 22-item 'Job/Activity Satisfaction' measure, which captured information from 415 respondents engaged in the different types of employment, along four (4) key dimensions: 'Respect and Recognition,' 'Job/Market Stability,' 'Workload and Stress,' and 'Self-Efficacy.' This paper summarizes some of the salient results from the scale and from its corresponding index.

Our findings revealed that both entrepreneurs and wage earners in Trinidad and Tobago were far more satisfied with those aspects of work over which they had sovereignty than with those controlled by their employers (for paid workers) or by market conditions (for entrepreneurs). Those areas of low satisfaction in the work environment could be targeted for improvement by employers seeking to improve labour conditions. Differences in satisfaction levels between entrepreneurs and paid employees were observed in several areas. Entrepreneurs reported greater levels of work satisfaction overall than did paid employees. Further, while only 30% of entrepreneurs signalled their intent to transition from entrepreneurship to alternative employment (full-time or part-time paid employment), a disproportionately large percentage of paid employees (76%) aspired to full-time or part-time entrepreneurship. Some of this may be due to a willingness to trade the stability of a guaranteed pay check for autonomy and versatility, two qualities which, although almost synonymous with self-employment, could be introduced by creative employers into the work environment.

Sex, age and ethnicity were also found to be significant main predictors of work satisfaction. The combined (interactive) effects of sex, ethnicity, and employment type on satisfaction also proved interesting, highlighting where there are gaps between self- and wage-employed workers for men and for women of different ethnicities. These outcomes suggest a need for more robust, evidence-based industrial relations policies and possible areas for focussed attention by employers in Trinidad and Tobago which can help to improve employee satisfaction and, ultimately, organizational performance.

Keywords: *work/job satisfaction; entrepreneurship; workplace trends; quality of life; multivariate index; industrial relations; Trinidad and Tobago*

1.0. Introduction

People engage in work for numerous reasons. Among others, these include financial motivations and the need for self-actualization. Notwithstanding, most adults spend a substantial portion of their adult lives at work (Judge, Piccolo, Podsakoff, Shaw & Rich, 2010). Quite often, individuals also devote a significant amount of time commuting to and from work or performing other work-related activities. Thus, from a human development perspective, work satisfaction is assumed to be crucial to happiness and wellbeing so that overall quality of life (QoL) can be improved by enhancing job satisfaction (Makabe, Takagai, Asanuma, Ohtomo & Kimura, 2015). Given its impacts, job satisfaction has been found to correlate positively with employee commitment and retention, and with organizational productivity and effectiveness (Latif et al, 2013; Deery & Jago, 2015). Workers, therefore, whether paid or self-employed, play an integral role in macroeconomic performance.

While work/job satisfaction among paid employees has garnered much attention among scholars and practitioners of various backgrounds across the globe – as demonstrated by numerous pertinent research studies – there is still a dearth of research on issues surrounding labour and employment in Trinidad and Tobago and, by extension, the region. Moreover, studies on work/job satisfaction conducted in Trinidad and Tobago (e.g. Naidu, Gobin, Ashraph, Newton & Gibbons, 2002; Naidu, Newton & Ayers, 2006; Mitchell & Esnard, 2014; Onuoha et al., 2017), are often limited in scope, since they typically examine this issue for paid employees within specific sectors, usually the health sector. To our knowledge, there are no empirical studies which explore levels of job satisfaction among the general populace of Trinidad and Tobago, nor are there works which investigate how job satisfaction levels vary within the population on the basis of socio-demographics. Paradoxically, Trinidad and Tobago's working population comprises approximately 602,000 persons (GoRTT, 2018), and the country's labour environment remains volatile across the many sectors throughout which the workforce is spread, with industrial disputes, inclusive of labour-related protests, being relatively common. There is an ever-present need for change within the country's industrial landscape. Organizational and national policies are critical in this regard. However, where there is little contextual understanding of job satisfaction, employers and policymakers may be limited in their abilities to frame evidence-based policies which produce effective and sustainable outcomes.

Hence, within a broader overarching study of Quality of Life (QoL), the authors did an assessment of work satisfaction as experienced by a Trinidad and Tobago sample of self-employed and paid workers. Rather than test existing hypotheses, the study, used an inductive approach to answer the following questions:

1. In what elements of job/activity satisfaction, as operationalized by the authors, are the largest gaps observed between self-employed and paid workers in Trinidad and Tobago?
2. How do individual demographic variables, such as sex, age, ethnicity, education, and marital status interact with employment type to impact job satisfaction?

3. What implications do our findings have for paid employees in Trinidad and Tobago?

2.0. Literature Review

2.1. Job Satisfaction and its Implications

Job satisfaction may be defined as “a positive feeling about a job, resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics” (Robbins & Judge, 2013, p.74). When, on the other hand, a job evokes negative emotions within an individual, dissatisfaction is said to have occurred (Armstrong, 2006). This is one of the most widely researched topics in the fields of human resource management and organizational behaviour (Snipes, Oswald, LaTour & Armenakis, 2005). Cranny, Smith and Stone (1992) estimated that there is in excess of 5,000 published works on job satisfaction. A reoccurring theme among many of these studies has been the precursors of job satisfaction and the implications of satisfaction/dissatisfaction on performance outcomes, both at the individual and at the organizational levels (Millán, Hessels, Thurik & Aguado, 2013). More specifically, past studies have shown a positive association between job satisfaction and employee performance, commitment and retention (Sousa-Poza & Sousa-Poza, 2000; Deery & Jago, 2015), productivity and effectiveness (Koys, 2001; Latif et al., 2013), profitability (Latif et al., 2013), competitiveness (Millán et al., 2013; Mahmood et al., 2019), service quality (Malhotra & Mukherjee, 2004), and customer satisfaction (Yoon, Beatty & Suh, 2001; Gazzoli, Hancer & Park, 2010, Brown and Lam, 2008). Meanwhile, absenteeism and increased turnover, amid other problems, may emerge where job satisfaction is low (Clark, 2001; Mahdi et al., 2012). Employee satisfaction, therefore, is integral to organizational success (Mullins & Christy, 2010, 2010; Teck-Hong & Waheed, 2011).

2.2. Theories of Job Satisfaction

Literature studies support the notion that job satisfaction is a multifaceted concept, with the level of satisfaction contingent on many factors (Robbins & Judge, 2007). However, the exact nature of these factors remains a source of debate, leading to numerous current theories of job satisfaction. However, Herzberg’s Two Factor Theory of Motivation and Job Satisfaction is by far the most common. Herzberg, Mausner & Snyderman (1959), attempting to empirically study job satisfaction, identified two sets of factors which impact on workers’ satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The first, referred to as ‘extrinsic’ or ‘hygiene’ factors, are concerned with the job environment. According to Herzberg et al., these aspects of the job, when present, prevent dissatisfaction. The authors, however, considered satisfaction and dissatisfaction as two discrete constructs, rather than parts of the same emotional scale. Based on this theory, therefore, while the absence of hygiene factors would likely result in dissatisfaction, their presence does not necessarily lead to satisfaction (Gibson, Ivanevich, Donnelly & Konopaske, 2012; Mullins, 2007). Herzberg et al. categorized salary, job security, working conditions, interpersonal relationships (including relationships with superiors and subordinates), and organizational policies and practices as the extrinsic factors of job satisfaction. Notably, these parallel Maslow’s lower

level needs – physiological needs and needs for safety and love (Dartey-Baah & Amoako, 2011; Mullins, 2007). The second set of factors, described as ‘intrinsic’ (but also referred to as ‘motivators’ or ‘satisfiers’), are those related to the job content and nature. These include the need for achievement and recognition, degree of responsibility, and opportunities for growth and advancement (Mullins, 2007).

Despite its wide utility, Herzberg’s theory has not escaped criticism. Detractors, for instance, frown at Herzberg’s assumption that extrinsic and intrinsic factors are mutually exclusive (Jain, 2005; Yusoff, Kian & Idris, 2013, and several others). They propose, rather, that hygiene factors may be useful as satisfiers and vice versa. According to Jain, the model put forward by Herzberg grossly oversimplifies the mechanisms via which satisfaction and dissatisfaction arise, as “satisfaction and dissatisfaction can reside in the job context, the job content or both jointly” (Jain, 2005, p. 128). Yusoff et al., in a subsequent work, point out a number of experimental studies which support Jain’s opinion.

2.3. The Precursors of Job Satisfaction

The discourse surrounding those factors which influence job satisfaction is broad and mixed. We therefore limit our discussion to five precursors of job satisfaction which are frequently cited within the literature. These are *compensation*, *social recognition*, *job security*, *interpersonal relationships*, and *opportunities for growth and advancement*.

Compensation

Compensation, inclusive of pay and fringe benefits, is considered one of the most impactful determinants of job satisfaction (Spector, 1997; Artz, 2010). Countless researchers have explored the link between these two variables. Evidence drawn from their works typically suggests that compensation is positively associated with job satisfaction (Baughman, 2003; Tessema, Ready & Embaye, 2013). Given this relationship, larger compensation packages have the potential to enhance satisfaction (Weiss, 2002; Caligiuri, Lepak & Bonache, 2010; Guan et al., 2014); the reverse is also true (Baughman, 2003). According to equity theorists, employees seek fair rewards for work done (Robbins, 2003). In the absence of this perceived fairness, they will attempt to restore equity. Such attempts usually lead to counterproductive behaviours in the workplace, like absenteeism, tardiness, thefts, and turnover (Currall, Towler, Judge & Kohn, 2005; Greenberg & Baron, 2008; Singh & Loncan, 2010).

Social recognition

While salary and other financial incentives are indispensable to job satisfaction, non-cash rewards (certificates, plaques, trophies, etc.) also improve job satisfaction by leaving a long-term positive emotional impact on an employee (Ford, Sturman & Heaton, 2012). Non-cash rewards are therefore cost-effective methods for improving workplace satisfaction (Ford et al., 2012). In addition, non-tangible rewards (e.g. timely positive feedback from superiors, verbal appreciation, a ‘pat on the

back,' and other forms of recognition) increase morale and self-esteem and reinforce positive behaviours like creativity among workers (Lawler, 2003; Nelson, 2005; Robbins & Judge, 2005; Stevenson, 2016). These types of recognition have the most impact on extrinsically motivated employees (Donata, 2011).

Job security

Job security has also been identified as a significant determinant of job satisfaction (Artz & Kaya, 2014). Sousa-Poza and Sousa-Poza (2000) found this result to be consistent across several countries. Job security has been positively linked with commitment and job performance (Yousef, 1998), as well as overall psychological well-being (Wichert, Nolan & Burchell, 2000). In contrast, workers who feel insecure in their jobs tend to report greater levels of dissatisfaction and increased turnover intentions (Sverke, Hellgren & Näswall, 2002).

Interpersonal relationships

Cohesiveness and opportunities to forge friendships at work have also been found to enhance job satisfaction and commitment among employees, and may limit incidents of turnover (Markiewicz, Devine & Kausilas, 2000; Morris, 2004), as they foster camaraderie, and provide moral and emotional support for workers. Employees who experience better relationships at work (with co-workers, superiors and subordinates) are likely to experience greater levels of job satisfaction than those who face alternative realities.

Need for growth and opportunities for advancement

Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000) rests on the principle that humans are growth oriented in nature and seek to self-actualize. Promotion provides an avenue for individuals to satisfy these needs (Robbins, 2003), and generally signifies increased income, improved status and additional autonomy. Naturally then, opportunities for promotion have been found to directly influence job satisfaction (Lambert, Hogan & Barton, 2001; Saari & Judge, 2004; Schermerhorn, Hunt & Osborn, 2005). When opportunities for promotion are perceived, one can anticipate greater levels of job satisfaction and fewer incidents of turnover (Shields & Ward, 2001). Where employees perceive that there is no room for upward mobility, or where they gauge the promotion process to be unfair or otherwise ineffective, job satisfaction inevitably decreases. Such an outcome, as previously discussed, may give rise to other unfavourable circumstances.

2.4. Job Satisfaction in Paid Versus Self-Employed Workers

Several studies have compared levels of job satisfaction for paid versus self-employed workers. Evidence from these studies often supports the view that, despite earning lower incomes (Hamilton, 2000; Benz & Frey, 2008), self-employed individuals are consistently more satisfied than paid employees (Hundley, 2001; Blanchflower, 2000; Bradley & Roberts, 2004; Benz & Frey, 2008; Millán,

Hessels, Thurik & Aguado, 2013). Frey, Benz and Stutzer (2004) offer the idea of '*procedural utility*' as an explanation for this anomaly. This concept suggests that, while people value outcomes, they likewise value the procedures which lead to those outcomes. According to Frey et al., while individuals (whether paid or self-employed) desire procedural utility in their capacity as income earners, self-employed persons obtain more of it from their work. The authors found that this trend had persisted even when income was controlled for. Frey et al. posit that independence and freedom – usually analogous with self-employment, but seldom enjoyed by paid employees who typically function in hierarchical, less autonomous settings – allows self-employed individuals to achieve new levels of flexibility in their working hours and in their work tasks. These, in turn, help to raise their levels of job satisfaction.

There is a lot of evidence to suggest that self-employed individuals possess high levels of optimism, self-efficacy, and other specific personality traits (Cassar, 2010; McGee, Peterson, Mueller & Sequeira, 2009). Bradley and Roberts (2004) found that these traits also partially accounted for the observed positive correlation between self-employment and job satisfaction, since they are, in and of themselves, reliable predictors of job satisfaction.

Given the disparities in levels of job satisfaction for paid versus self-employed workers, research has found that discontentment among paid employees is a major push factor into self-employment (Guerra & Patuelli, 2014), as unhappy wage earners seek alternative avenues for boosting work-related satisfaction.

3.0. Methodology

As previously indicated, this exploration of job/activity satisfaction was part of a larger Quality of Life (QoL) study conducted via an inductive approach. QoL measures are recognized as being grounded in the societies for which they are developed, and therefore to have no generalizability even from sample to sample within the same population. Our desire was to develop a measure - an algorithm extracted via statistically valid techniques and applied to data collected from scales of generic elements of satisfaction for multiple domains of satisfaction, challenges, and influences - which would be independent of sample and of population. To do so we operationalized the scale constructs using, *inter alia*, a variety of inputs, which included interrogating local and international work experiences, considering some concepts raised in literature studies, and incorporating some views of entrepreneurs from a qualitative exploratory study we conducted as another part of the larger project.

3.1. Data Collection and Sampling

A proprietary structured survey was developed by the researchers for use in this study. The instrument was administered online via Survey Monkey® from September 2016 to November 2017. The survey link was sent by email to entrepreneurs listed in the business section of the local telephone directory, to various Chambers of Commerce, to the organizers of UpMarket – a weekly entrepreneurial

fair, to the Agricultural Society of Trinidad and Tobago, and to other professional institutions for distribution to their members. It was distributed to staff and students at the University of Trinidad and Tobago, to individuals on various social media platforms – ‘Linkedin,’ ‘Facebook,’ and ‘Whatsapp’ – and to general members of the public. A snowball effect was applied, as people receiving the survey link were asked to forward it to their acquaintances. The snowball effect is usually considered to be a non-probabilistic approach to sample selection, as it captures people of similar characteristics, mindsets and habits (Johnson, 2014). However, this approach is considered to be random and unbiased in this case, as the initial rollout of the survey link targeted a broadly diverse group of potential respondents and the researchers did not exhibit any control over who received the survey,

The instrument, designed to capture views and experiences from entrepreneurs, wage earners, and individuals engaged both in entrepreneurship and in paid employment, consisted of demographic questions about the respondent and likewise his/her activity (business or employment), closed questions requiring categorical responses, and eight scales with questions designed to measure several domains, including the level of satisfaction experienced by the respondents in various aspects of their work – the Job/Activity Satisfaction scale with 22 items. Interval scales with an absolute zero were used. These returned responses from ‘0’ (no satisfaction) to ‘5’ (complete satisfaction) for each manifest variable on the scale in question. This type of scale has previously been used by researchers at the University of Trinidad and Tobago (Ramdwar, Stoute & Ganpat, 2015; Chadee & Stoute, 2018).

3.2. Statistical Analysis

The data was exported to SPSS V.22 for analysis. The survey data was summarized, and each scale checked for reliability, as estimated by its Cronbach alpha value. Scales were converted into individual indexes, as described below, and different combinations of them were tested for suitability as an overall Quality of Life (QoL) index. All demographics and categorical perceptions were summarized as frequency distributions. Scale items were summarized as means and standard deviations.

3.2.1. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

EFA, using Principal Component Analysis followed by Varimax rotation, was performed in order to extract latent orthogonal Factors from each survey scale. Only Factors with eigen values greater than 1.0 were extracted. The variance explained by each Factor was noted. Variables with Factor loadings larger than 0.5 were considered as correlated strongly enough to the Factor to characterize its essence or theme. The regression scores for each Factor were saved to be used in future analyses. The goodness of fit of the solution was estimated from the value of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic (better when closer to 1.0), the off-diagonal elements of the Anti-image correlation matrix (in a good Factor model, these values are closer to zero), and the significance ($p < 0.05$) of the Bartlett’s test of sphericity.

3.2.2. Development of scale scores, index scores, and a Job Satisfaction index

For the Job/Activity Satisfaction scale, scores for all respondents could be obtained by combining the Factors into a weighted average, using the variance explained by the Factor as its weight. For index scores, however, a general independent algorithm for the index was obtained by following a previously developed methodology (Chadee and Stoute, 2018). The algorithm for the scale index was a linear combination of weights and scale variable/item scores. Once the scale is administered to any sample of individuals, the scores given to all the scale items by each respondent, R , can be plugged into the algorithm associated with the scale, to get a single index score, I_R , for that respondent. I_R is obtained by adding the weighted scale scores for all n items, as in equation (2) below, in which S_j was the score for the j^{th} of n scale items, and the weight for that item, W_j , was estimated in the first step of the process. For each scale for which p Factors are extracted in this study, the weight for the j^{th} scale statement was obtained by summing over all of the p Factors the product of the regression Factor score coefficients (β_{ij}) for the j^{th} scale item and the variances (V_i) explained by the Factors. This is shown in equation 1.

$$W_j = (\sum_{i=1}^p V_i \beta_{ij}) / V \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$I_R = (\sum_{j=1}^n W_j S_j) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The Job/Activity Satisfaction Index scores were used in further statistical analyses.

3.2.3. General Linear Model (GLM) for indexes

The significant impacting main and interaction effects of several demographics, including ‘employment type,’ on the respondents’ Job/Activity Satisfaction index scores were estimated using a univariate General Linear Model (GLM). Significant main and interaction effects were recorded. LSD *post hoc* tests were used to determine effect sizes for the significant impacting factors.

3.2.4. Regression Analysis

A regression model, controlled for sample demographics and employment type, was estimated for the Job/Activity Satisfaction index using a forward step-wise procedure, with other indexes from the larger study as possible predictors. Residual Analysis was used to test the assumptions of normality, independence and heteroscedasticity. The Durbin-Watson statistic was obtained as a corroborating measure to ensure there were no patterns (runs of positive or negative values) in the residuals. Collinearity statistics were checked in order to test for multicollinearity in the independent factors. The goodness of fit of the model was given by the coefficient of determination (R^2 and R^2_{adj}) and by the significance of the F statistic for the ANOVA test of the model as a whole. The significance of each slope coefficient was checked using t tests.

3.2.5. Discriminant Analysis

A potential classification model for entrepreneurial activity (self-employed/wage-employed) was explored using step-wise Discriminant Analysis, with all other demographics and all indexes (those

measuring motivations, idealistic perceptions of quality of life, activity barriers, and satisfaction) as potential significant classifiers. Box's M tested the equality of means. The goodness of fit of the classification was obtained from the correct classification percentage.

4.0. Results and Discussion

A structured survey, which elicited 415 responses, was administered online using Survey Monkey®, to persons in paid employment, to those who were self-employed, and to those who were paid employees supplementing their incomes with some business activity. The characteristics of the sample, in particular individual and work/activity demographics, provide contexts for the participants' views so it is important to summarize these first before going into deeper analysis of those views. In this survey instrument, there were also some preliminary questions before the scales which captured interesting insights into the realities, perceptions and preferences of survey respondents regarding their current work activities. These will be covered briefly in section 4.3.

4.1. Individual demographics

Respondents were mostly female (61%), within the 25 to 40 age group (52%), married (48%), highly educated (53% with non-professional tertiary education, and 20% with professional tertiary education), and residing in East Trinidad (Tunapuna/Piarco [15%], Arima [8%], San Juan/Laventille [7%], Sangre Grande [2%]). There were almost equal sub-samples of Afro-, Indo-, and mixed Trinbagonians among the respondents -Table 1.

Table 1: Individual demographics of survey respondents

Demographic	Category	Frequency (%)
SEX	Male	39
	Female	61
AGE	18 to 24 years	14
	25 to 40 years	52
	41 to 54 years	22
	55 and older	11
AREA OF RESIDENCE	Arima	8
	Chaguanas	10
	Couva/Tabaquite/Talparo	12
	Diego Martin	10
	Mayaro/Rio Claro	1
	Penal/Debe	1
	Point Fortin	4
	Port-of-Spain	11
	Princes Town	3
	San Fernando	10
	San Juan/Laventille	7
	Sangre Grande	2
	Siparia	2
	Tobago	3
	Tunapuna/Piarco	15
ETHNICITY	Afro-Trinidadian	30
	Indo-Trinidadian	35
	Caucasian/Syrian/Lebanese	6

Demographic	Category	Frequency (%)
	Chinese	0
	Mixed	30
MARITAL STATUS	Single (never married)	45
	Married/domestic partnership	48
	Divorced/separated/widowed	8
EDUCATION	Primary or less	0.5
	Secondary	11
	Technical/vocational/certificate	16
	Professional tertiary degree	20
	Non-professional tertiary degree	53

4.2. Job/Activity demographics

The frequency distributions are shown in Table 2. Most respondents in the sample carried out their activities in the capital city of Port-of-Spain (28%), and most (44%) were paid employees. The majority of self-employed individuals in this sample were business owners for 5 years or less (52%), while paid employees were mostly employed for 11-20 years (34%). The self-employed worked in smaller companies – 1 to 5 employees (66 %) or 6 to 25 (29%). However, the majority of paid employees (56%) worked in large companies with 50 employees or more. The study participants were engaged in several diverse activities.

Table 2: Work (activity) demographics of survey respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (%)
JOB/ACTIVITY CATEGORY	Never worked previously	2.9
	Currently unemployed or retired	9.3
	Self-employed	14.7
	Paid employee	43.9
	Paid employee and entrepreneur	29.2
LOCATION OF ACTIVITY	Arima	5.4
	Chaguanas	7.9
	Couva/Tabaquite/Talparo	12.1
	Diego Martin	2.1
	Mayaro/Rio Claro	0.5
	Penal/Debe	0.3
	Point Fortin	2.6
	Port-of-Spain	27.9
	Princes Town	1.3
	San Fernando	11.0
	San Juan/Laventille	7
	Sangre Grande	0
	Siparia	0.8
Tobago	3	
Tunapuna/Piarco	18	
LENGTH OF ENGAGEMENT (Self-employed-partial or full) n=235	<5 years	52
	5-10 years	22
	11-20 years	17
	21-30 years	6
	>30 years	3
LENGTH OF EMPLOYMENT	<5 years	19
	5-10 years	26
	11-20 years	34

Variable	Category	Frequency (%)			
(Paid Employee-partial or full) n=347	21-30 years	11			
	>30 years	10			
NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES		Total	Self.	Paid	Both
	1-5	30.8	65.5	9.1	44.8
	6-25	23.5	29.3	22.9	20.7
	26-50	8.6	3.4	12.0	6.9
	> 50	37.1	1.7	56.0	27.6

4.3. Realities and preferences within current activities

Generally, a larger percentage of individuals in paid employment (53%), rather than in self-employment (24%), were engaged in the activity for very long hours (9 to 16, or 17 to 24) during the week. The reverse was true on Saturdays and Sundays, when 13% of those engaged in entrepreneurial activities worked for long hours, compared to 8% of those in paid employment. This is somewhat counter-intuitive but real for this sample. Prior to their current or most recent activity (self-employment or paid employment), more than half of the participants (52.1%) were engaged in alternative employment. These individuals, therefore, had grounds for comparison of the two employment types. The bulk of the participants (51.5%) chose self-employment as their preferred activity. Most participants (75.1%) expressed confidence in their ability to easily transition from one type of employment to the next. Interestingly, 64.8% also admitted that they intended to transition from their current or most recent type of employment. When these choices were examined in more detail, using chi square tests, it was found that there were significant associations between these sentiments and the respondents' current job/activity status. A larger percentage of self-employed than wage-employed individuals had been engaged in alternative employment prior to their current activity (82% versus 42%) and preferred their own current type of employment (74% versus 35%). A smaller percentage of self-employed respondents, being significantly more satisfied in their current pursuits, planned to transition into an alternative type of employment in the future (30% compared with 76% of paid employees). Examination in the next section of the individual scale item means for each employment sub-group illustrates clearly the micro reasons for that overall sentiment.

4.4. Summary statistics

The mean scores and other summary statistics for the elements on the Job/Activity Satisfaction scale are broken out for the two groups, self-employed and paid employees, in Table 3. The elements are arranged in order of descending mean scores for paid employees. The larger the mean for any element, the more satisfied, on average, are the individuals in the sample with that aspect of their job (paid employees) or business activity (self-employed). The larger the standard deviation, the more variation/polarization there is in the responses to the scale question. The sign and magnitude of the skewness coefficient both yield information. The more negative and the larger the skewness coefficient, the greater the preponderance of larger scores given in response to a certain scale element/question.

The objective in this paper is not to show a simple comparison between paid and self-employed workers or to understand the boost, if any, that self-employment can give to Quality of Life (which was the objective of the broader study). Instead, the focus here is on paid labour and what can be done to enhance the industrial environment for workers. To do this we look first at elements of their work environment with which paid employees are least satisfied but also at those activity elements for which there exists the biggest gaps in satisfaction between self-employed and paid workers. The argument follows then that if the spirit of entrepreneurship, in those areas where self-employed individuals are more satisfied, could be duplicated somewhat in the work environment for paid employees, it should increase satisfaction. In the last column of Table 3 are the mean gaps in satisfaction for each scale element. Gaps in the mean scores of 0.8 or more are highlighted in blue (0.80 to 0.95) and red (1.05 to 1.32). These represent anywhere from 28% to 78% difference in mean scores between the groups.

The same elements engender satisfaction at the top for both groups but not at the bottom. Both sub-groups rate measures of personal accomplishment highest- confidence in their abilities to do the job, to engage in meaningful work/activity relationships, and to get ahead. Self-employed respondents were least satisfied with their income stability, with the sustainability (security) of their business, with their ability to access materials needed to carry out the activity, and with the levels of stress they suffer. Ironically, they were still more satisfied in each of these areas than were paid employees. In fact, paid employees scored lower in satisfaction on every single element of this scale. Three of the work elements which engendered the least satisfaction in paid workers were among those with the largest gaps in scores (1.09 to 1.32). The largest gaps between the two sub-groups were for the work elements of *equal pay for equal work, internal recognition of efforts, equal opportunity for advancement in the activity (promotion), opportunities for skill development, growth, and personal development, public respect for the activity, and variety in tasks*. These then should be the areas of focus for employers and labour consultants. Ensuring that there is equity, worker recognition, opportunities for self-improvement in the workplace and external respect for the organization itself, according to these results, would promote greater worker satisfaction.

Table 3: Summary statistics for sample sub-groups of self-employed and paid employed

SCALE ELEMENT	Paid Employee			Self-employed			Mean Diff
	M	S.D	Skew	M	S.D.	Skew	
Your own confidence in your capabilities to perform necessary tasks	3.68	1.36	-1.08	3.99	1.25	-1.59	0.31
Ability to foster meaningful (to the activity) relationships	3.05	1.57	-0.47	3.76	1.27	-0.96	0.71
Level of success/achievement possible	2.95	1.57	-0.43	3.78	1.32	-1.24	0.84
Income stability	2.73	1.61	-0.31	2.94	1.51	-0.31	0.21
Work hours	2.73	1.67	-0.30	3.17	1.62	-0.62	0.44
Your level of creative input	2.68	1.54	-0.24	3.74	1.47	-1.06	0.80

SCALE ELEMENT	Paid Employee			Self-employed			Mean Diff
	M	S.D	Skew	M	S.D.	Skew	
Public respect for the activity	2.68	1.52	-0.19	3.49	1.45	-0.80	1.07
The degree of autonomy you hold- (ability to make decisions in your area)	2.64	1.47	-0.21	3.59	1.57	-0.86	0.95
Flexibility in work hours	2.59	1.75	-0.13	3.47	1.70	-0.77	0.88
Job (business) security	2.54	1.63	-0.17	2.97	1.62	-0.30	0.43
Workload	2.41	1.61	0.02	3.00	1.56	-0.43	0.59
Opportunities for skills development	2.39	1.64	-0.03	3.56	1.57	-0.79	1.16
Market (for product or services) stability	2.39	1.63	-0.08	3.12	1.38	-0.36	0.73
Ability to access materials or facilities needed for the employment or entrepreneurial activity	2.39	1.57	-0.02	2.96	1.51	-0.31	0.58
Variety in tasks	2.32	1.60	0.10	3.42	1.46	-0.54	1.10
Opportunities for growth and personal development	2.30	1.69	-0.01	3.35	1.67	-0.61	1.05
Flexibility in work location	2.27	1.77	0.14	3.21	1.73	-0.54	0.94
Support from others	2.22	1.50	0.08	3.01	1.51	-0.24	0.79
Stress levels	2.06	1.67	0.34	2.73	1.60	-0.19	0.67
Equal pay for equal work	2.01	1.69	0.23	3.18	1.70	-0.52	1.16
Internal Recognition of efforts	1.97	1.54	0.18	3.05	1.71	-0.39	1.09
Equal opportunity for paid job advancement or building market share (entrepreneur)	1.72	1.60	0.37	3.04	1.67	-0.36	1.32

4.5. Reliability and Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

The reliability of the Job/Activity satisfaction scale was estimated by obtaining its Cronbach alpha value, which is 0.955. This a large scale of 22 items so that such a large alpha value establishes this scale as clearly measuring a single latent construct. That interpretation of the Cronbach alpha is more germane in this case than just describing it as ‘reliable,’ especially given the potential argument that reliability is often rooted in the sample. Being able to operationalize job/activity satisfaction so completely augurs well for the generalizability of this scale to other samples in this population and other populations.

A good Factor solution was obtained for this scale. This was estimated from a high value of 0.932 for the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic for sampling adequacy, small off-diagonal elements in the anti-image (AIC) correlation matrix, and a significant ($p=0.000$) Bartlett’s test for sphericity. Four orthogonal Factors, each representing a separate dimension of Job/Activity Satisfaction, were identified: ‘*Respect and Recognition*,’ (the extent to which the activity provided avenues for personal and professional growth, fostered creativity, and promoted public respect); ‘*Job/Market Stability*,’ (the degree to which the materials required to engage in the activity were readily available, as well as the amount of security respondents felt in the job or business); ‘*Workload and Stress*,’ (features such as flexibility in work hours and location, having a job that offers diversity in tasks, and having a sensible

workload); and '*Self-efficacy*' (the degree of confidence respondents had in their own abilities to successfully execute the various aspects of their jobs or activities, along with confidence in other areas). These four Factors together explained 70.3% of the total variance in Job/Activity Satisfaction scores.

It is a clean solution with most of the 22 scale items loading heavily (>0.50) on one and only one Factor. Exceptions to this were the three variables *equal opportunity for advancement*, *equal pay for equal work*, and *internal recognition for efforts*. These loaded on both the first and second Factors. There was one item, *support from others*, which loaded on/was correlated with no Factor with a correlation greater than 0.47, its loading for the '*Workload and Stress*' dimension.

The themes of the Factors extracted in the EFA need to be considered with the results of the last section. First, we make the observation that Job/Activity Satisfaction is not a simple construct, with its multi-dimensional structure (4 factors) compared to our 'Home Life Satisfaction' scale (one single factor) and our 'Material Comforts' scale (two clean Factors representing '*Basic Necessities*' and '*Discretionary Expenses*'), as observed in our larger study but not shown here. The Job/Activity Satisfaction themes fall into the sub-domains of the personal (self-efficacy), organizational (respect & recognition, workload and stress), and macroeconomic or market forces (job/market stability). Mean item scores were among the highest in both sub-groups (paid employee and self-employed) for items which loaded on the dimension, '*Self-efficacy*,' namely *confidence in one's own ability to do the job or activity* (3.68 or 3.99), *to foster meaningful relationships* (3.05 or 3.76), and *to attain the desired level of self-advancement* (2.95 or 3.78)

Employers are already doing, for themselves, all they can do to build their businesses within the macro-economy. Workers seem not to be lacking in satisfaction with their self-efficacy. However, the organizational factors are certainly areas in which employers can and, from the trends seen with this sample, need to effect improvement. Six of the seven elements which result in the largest gaps (>1.0) in satisfaction between paid- and self-employed individuals load on the first Factor, '*Recognition and Respect*.' Four of the next five largest gaps are also for items which load on the first and on the other organizational Factor, '*Workload and Stress*.' These items are highlighted in the same blue and red colours in Table 4 to match the items in Table 3.

Table 4: Factors extracted in Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Factor	Job/Activity Satisfaction Scale Elements (70.3%), $\alpha = 0.955$
1	<p>Respect and Recognition (20.8%)-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities for personal growth, skills development, and advancement in the job or business activity • Autonomy, • Creative input, • Fair remuneration, • Recognition, and • Public respect
2	<p>Job/Market Stability (18.5%)-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job/business security, • Steadiness of income, and • Market stability (including easy access to needed materials)
3	<p>Workload and Stress (18.0%)-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length and flexibility of work hours, • Flexibility in work location, • Workloads, • Variety in work tasks/activities, • Stress levels, and. • Support from others (loading only 0.47)
4	<p>Self-efficacy (13.0%)-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confidence in one's ability to perform necessary tasks • Confidence in one's ability to foster relationships in the workplace, and • Confidence to attain a desirable level of achievement.

4.6. Index Construction and Summary

Job/Activity Satisfaction index values for each individual in the sample were obtained by combining scale item scores for that individual into a weighted average, using as weights the product of the variance explained by the factor and of the score coefficients from the EFA. Note these weights are independent of the individual or the sample so that the index becomes a tool which could be used for any sample. One need only administer the scale and multiply the item scores by the weights which have been estimated in this study. The index values could change from one sample to the next within one population and also be different from population to population depending on the scale scores for the particular sample of individuals but the algorithm (the linear combination of the products of weights and scale item scores) remains unchangeable. The combined satisfaction index was developed from the three dimensions of satisfaction, the weighted average of this 'Job/Activity' measure plus the indexes for 'Home Life' and 'Material Comforts.' The summary statistics are listed in Table 5 for the Job/Activity Satisfaction and overall QoL indexes. For both indexes, there is a gap in scores, 0.56 for Job/Activity Satisfaction and 0.95 for the QoL. The mean satisfaction gap between the self- and wage

employed in job/activity is a bigger proportion (33%) of the lower score, than is that for their overall QoL (17%), a reminder that a job or an activity is not the sole determinant of the QoL one enjoys.

Table 5: Summary statistics for Job/Activity and overall QoL index

Index	Statistic	Wage Employee	Self-Employed
Job/Activity Satisfaction	Mean	1.70	2.26
	Minimum	.00	.04
	Maximum	3.30	3.49
	S.D.	.76	.81
	Skewness	-.01	-.49
Combined Satisfaction/Overall QoL	Mean	5.56	6.51
	Minimum	.83	1.24
	Maximum	9.69	9.97
	S.D.	1.96	1.97
	Skewness	-.07	-.37

The weights assigned to the individual Job/Activity Satisfaction scale items are estimates of the importance of each item to job satisfaction. While respondents were most satisfied with their own abilities to achieve certain specific outcomes, these were the items with the least weights in the index (e.g. confidence in one's own abilities to perform well on the job [0.017], and ability to foster meaningful relationships on the job [0.025]). The largest contributors to the Job/Activity Satisfaction index scores were 'opportunities for growth and personal development,' and 'for skill development,' 'equal opportunity for job advancement,' 'internal recognition of efforts,' and 'degree of autonomy/ability to make decisions.' Each was similarly weighted (0.038 or 0.037). These important items to satisfaction speak to the need for proper policies at the organizational level.

4.6. General Linear Model (GLM) of Job/Activity Satisfaction Index

The impact of demographics on the Job/Activity Satisfaction Index was examined using a GLM analysis. The results are expressed in equation 3 and with some more detail in Table 6. This model explained 43% (R^2) of the variability in index scores for this sample. Age, ethnicity, and employment type were all significant ($p < 0.05$) main effects impacting the satisfaction obtained from work. Individuals of mixed ancestry, those engaged in entrepreneurship, and those 41 years or older are estimated to enjoy more job/activity satisfaction. Sex, however, features only in two interactions, one 3-way and one 4-way, with ethnicity and employment type. These interactions were both significant at the 10% critical level. The three-way interaction plots are shown in Figure 1.

$$\text{Job/Activity Satisfaction Index} = \text{Employment Type} + \text{Ethnicity} + \text{Age} + \text{Sex} * \text{ethnicity} * \text{employment type} \quad (\mathbf{p=0.067}) + \text{Sex} * \text{ethnicity} * \text{education} * \text{employment type} \quad (\mathbf{p=0.053})$$

$$\mathbf{R^2 = 0.431} \quad \mathbf{(3)}$$

Table 6: Details of GLM model for Job/Activity Satisfaction Index

Dependent Variable	Main Effects	Interacting Effects	R ²
Job/Activity Satisfaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnicity (0.023) Mixed > African (p=0.026) Mixed > Indian (p=0.016) • Employment type (p=0.013) Self-employed > paid employee • Age: 55+ ≈ 41-54 > 25-40 ≈ 18-24 (p=0.000) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex * ethnicity * employment type (p=0.067) • Sex * ethnicity * education * employment type (p=0.053) 	0.431

Figure 1: Plots of impact of 3-way interaction of Sex X Ethnicity X Employment type

Of most interest here is where the biggest gaps in satisfaction occur between self-employed and paid workers. For example, these gaps in satisfaction are large for Indians of either sex. For mixed-Trinbagonian men, there is no real gap but for mixed women, there is the largest satisfaction gap between the self- and paid employed. The reverse is true for Afro-Trinbagonians. There is a big gap for men and no gap in job/activity satisfaction for women in this ethnic sub-group. It is not as easy to map a 4-way interaction, so it is difficult to see how education changes these 3-way patterns in Figure 1, but the p value is even lower for that 4-way interaction than it is for the 3-way, which shows some pronounced trends, which could be significant in other samples.

Although the *age * sex * employment* interaction is not statistically significant, which could happen if there is too much intra-group variability in this sample, the interaction plots of these variables for the Job/Activity Satisfaction index show some interesting trends –Figure 2. The mean scores for the males increased with age across all employment types, and were consistently higher for entrepreneurs, regardless of age. Women ≥ 55 who engaged in entrepreneurship were much more satisfied with their work activity than women of all other age groups. Generally, for each employment type, the older women were usually more satisfied than the younger. A break in trend occurred for those engaged both in paid employment and entrepreneurship. This group's mean satisfaction dropped substantially and surprisingly. Perhaps, as women age, it becomes more difficult for them to balance both activities.

4.7. Regression and Discriminant Analysis

In this paper Regression and Discriminant Analysis are handled together because these two techniques yield only gross information about job/activity satisfaction. The fine details, which are more important to the question of what can be done to improve satisfaction in the workplace, are clearer in the earlier sections. Still the gross information does add some insight. In the case of regression, one gets a quantitative estimate of impact which is not possible from the GLM model. It also illustrates the other life domains which impact on job/activity satisfaction. Discriminant Analysis, on the other hand, estimates what other areas of satisfaction can be used to classify a worker as self- or wage employed.

The model for the Job/Activity satisfaction index is obtained from step-wise regression with the other indexes, controlled for the demographic variables of sex, age, employment type, education, and marital status. All assumptions of normality, independence, and homoscedasticity of the residuals and of the independent variables were tested and satisfied. The model, given in equation (4), explains 53% of the variance in Job/Activity Index scores. Sex and employment type, along with a number of other indexes, developed in the larger study, were significant predictors. Sex explained 5% of the variance, while employment type explained 12% of the variance. On average, scores for females were significantly lower than those for males (by 0.277), while scores for self-employed individuals were significantly higher than those of paid employees (by 0.356)

$$\text{Job/Activity Satisfaction Index scores} = 0.631 + 0.177 \times \text{Home Life Satisfaction} + 0.222 \times \text{Material Comforts} - 0.115 \times \text{Past Hindrances} + 0.107 \times \text{Influencing Factors} - 0.277 \times \text{Female} + 0.356 \times \text{Entrepreneur} \quad (4)$$

The results of the Discriminant Analysis estimate that, in this sample from Trinidad and Tobago, paid employees and self-employed individuals can be classified, with 70.3% correct classification accuracy, based on their Job/Activity Satisfaction and Home Life Satisfaction Index scores. Regression analysis, as seen from equation 4, predicts that, for all workers whether they are self-employed or paid employees, the satisfaction indexes are intertwined, along with indexes capturing the importance of past issues which may have hindered advancement as well as of those factors which may have influenced an individual to achieve the current satisfaction in his/her work activity. Discriminant Analysis, however, picks up only the combination of Home Life and Job/Activity satisfaction as differentiating between paid- and self-employed workers. Thus, with respect to the other indexes in the regression model, these two sub-groups are not distinct in their satisfaction.

Figure 2: Interaction plots (age x employment x sex) for job/activity satisfaction

5.0. Summary and Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the extent to which job satisfaction varies for paid versus self-employed workers in Trinidad and Tobago. Our study unearthed important trends which pertain to paid employment in Trinidad and Tobago, an area where there is still a dearth of research. Some of these trends could not be predicted in advance. Based on General Linear Modelling (GLM), Regression and Discriminant Analysis, self-employed individuals were found to have more work satisfaction on an overall gross level than paid employees. Evidence from means analysis of the individual scale variables show on a micro level the main areas in which the biggest gaps in satisfaction are registered. This analysis indicated that self-employed persons were, on average, more satisfied than paid employees in all aspects of their work.

As advantageous to work satisfaction that self-employment seems to be, from a practical standpoint, not everyone can venture into self-employment. Moreover, for those who do, the benefits gained from this transition are not always permanent (Georgellis & Yusuf, 2016). Thus, from a managerial perspective, what is required are microscopic evaluations of existing organizational and human resource policies and practices to identify gaps between existing realities and the employees' expectations. (This is especially needed given our finding that paid employees in Trinidad and Tobago are least satisfied with those aspects of their work governed by their employers.) Following such evaluations, changes should be instituted, where necessary, and where practically possible to narrow these gaps. In so doing, employers and managers can enhance feelings of job satisfaction for employees and, consequently, the success outcomes of the organization. While each organization may present its own unique set of challenges, we, on the basis of our findings, make the following general recommendations for employers seeking to improve labour conditions within their organizations/units:

- Creation of programs for recognizing and rewarding employee efforts, including formal programs for major achievements which contribute to the successful attainment of organizational goals;
- Gradual increases in levels of autonomy given to employees to motivate them and increase their levels of job satisfaction. Increased autonomy should also be considered as a reward strategy where practicable;
- Creation of a workspace within which employees can share and exercise creativity in the day-to-day operation of the organization;
- Introduction of variety and diversity in tasks, where possible. This can prevent monotony. At the same time, it can allow employees to expand their knowledge base, skills and talents and provide avenues for personal and professional development;
- Introduction of some degree of flexibility (in working hours and/or location) into the workplace, where feasible;

- Sustained monitoring and assessment of levels of job satisfaction among employees to gauge the effectiveness of programs and policies and to ensure levels of satisfaction among workers are maintained.

Works Cited

Armstrong, M. (2006). *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. 10th Edition, Kogan Page Publishing, London.

Armstrong, M. (2006). *Handbook of human resource management practice* (10th ed.). London, England: Kogan Page Ltd.

Artz, B. (2010). Fringe benefits and job satisfaction. *International Journal of Manpower*, 31(6), 626-644. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437721011073346>

Artz, B. & Kaya, I. (2014). The impact of job security on job satisfaction in economic contractions versus expansions. *Applied Economics*, 46(24), 2873-2890

Baughman, R., Dinardi, D., & Holtz-Eakin, D. (2003). Productivity and Wage Effects of ‘Family-Friendly’ Fringe Benefits. *International Journal of Manpower*, 24(3), 247-59.

Benz M., & Frey, B. (2008). Being independent is a great thing: Subjective evaluations of self-employment and hierarchy. *Economica*, 75(298), 362–383.

Blanchflower, D. G. (2000). Self-employment in OECD countries. *Labour Economics*, 7, 471–505.

Bradley, D. E., & Roberts, J. A. (2004). Self-employment and job satisfaction: Investigating the role of self-efficacy, depression and seniority. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 42(1), 37-58.

Brown, S. P., & Lam, S. K. (2008). A meta-analysis of relationships linking employee satisfaction to customer responses. *Journal of Retailing*, 84(3), 243-255, 2008.

Caligiuri P., Lepak D., & Bonache J. (2010). *Global Dimensions of Human Resources Management: Managing the Global Workforce*, Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Cassar, G. (2010). Are individuals entering self-employment overly-optimistic? An empirical test of plans and projections on nascent entrepreneur expectations. *Strategic Management Journal*, 31(8), 822-840.

Chadee, S., & Stoute, V. (2018). Development of an urban intensity index to facilitate urban ecosystem studies in Trinidad and Tobago. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 45(3), 508-527.

Clark, A. E. (2001). What really matters in a job? Hedonic measurement using quit data. *Labour Economics*, 8, 223-242.

Cranny, C.J., Smith, P.C., & Stone, E. (1992). *Job satisfaction: How people feel about their jobs*. Lexington Books, Lexington.

Currall, S. C., Towler, A. J., Judge, T. A., & Kohn, L. (2005). Pay satisfaction and organizational outcomes. *Personnel Psychology*, 58(3), 613-640.

Dartey-Baah, K., & Amoako, G. (2011). Application of Frederick Herzberg’s Two-Factor theory in assessing and understanding employee motivation at work: a Ghanaian Perspective. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(9), 1-8.

Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.

- Deery, M. and Jago, L. (2015). Revisiting talent management, work-life balance and retention strategies. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(3), 453-472.
- Donata, L. (2011). Employee motivation techniques: Extrinsic rewards vs. intrinsic rewards. *Leadership Management*, 2(3), 121-132.
- Frey, B. S., Benz, M. & Stutzer, A. (2004). Introducing procedural utility: Not only what, but also how matters. *Journal of Institutional and Theoretical Economics*, 160, 377-401.
- Gazzoli, G., Hancer, M. & Park, Y. (2010). Perception of service quality: A study in the restaurant industry. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 34(1), 56-77.
- Georgellis, Y. & Yusuf, A. (2016). Is becoming self-employed a panacea for job satisfaction? Longitudinal evidence from work to self-employment transitions. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 54, 53-76.
- Gibson, J. L., Ivanevich, J. M., Donnelly, J. H., & Konopaske, R. (2012). *Organisations: Behaviour, Structure, Processes* (14th ed.). Boston. McGraw-Hill.
- Government of the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago [GoRTT] (2018), *Review of the Economy: Turnaround*, Port of Spain: GoRTT. Retrieved from <https://www.finance.gov.tt/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Review-Of-The-Economy-2018.pdf>
- Greenberg, J., & Baron, R. A. (2008). *Behaviour in Organizations* (9th ed.). Pearson Education Inc., Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.
- Guan, Y., Wen, Y., Chen, S.X., Liu, H., Si, W., Liu, Y., & Dong, Z. (2014). When do salary and job level predict career satisfaction and turnover intention among Chinese managers? The role of perceived organizational career management and career anchor. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 23(4), 596-607.
- Guerra, G., & Patuelli, R. (2014). The role of job satisfaction in transitions into self-employment," *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 40(3):543-571.
- Hamilton, B. H. (2000). Does entrepreneurship pay? An empirical analysis of the returns to self-employment. *Journal of Political Economy*, 108 (3), 604-631.
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B.B. (1959). *The Motivation to Work* (2nd ed.). New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Hundley, G. (2001). Why and when are the self-employed more satisfied with their Work? *Industrial Relations*, 40(2), 293-316.
- Jain, N. K. (2005). *Organisational Behaviour* (Vol 1). Atlantic Publishers.
- Johnson, T. P. (2014). Snowball sampling: Introduction. Wiley StatsRef, Wiley and Sons, Chichester.
- Judge, T. A., Piccolo, R. F., Podsakoff, N. P., Shaw, C. J. & Rich, B. L. (2010). The relationship between pay and job satisfaction: a meta-analysis of the literature. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 77(2), 157-167.
- Koys, D. J. (2001). The effects of employee satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior, and turnover on organizational effectiveness: A unit-level, longitudinal study. *Personnel Psychology*, 54(1), 101-114.

- Latif, M. S., Ahmad, M., Qasim, M., Mushtaq, M., Ferdoos, A., & Naeem, H. (2015). Impact of employee's job satisfaction on organizational performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7, 166–171.
- Lambert, E. G., Hogan, N. L., & Barton, S. M. (2001). The impact of job satisfaction on turnover intent: a test of structural measurement model using a national sample of workers. *The Social Science Journal*, 38(2), 233-51.
- Lawler, E. E. (2003). *Treat people right*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Inc. McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Mahdi, A. F., Mohd Zin, M. Z., Mohd Nor, M. R., Sakat, A. A., & Abang Naim, A. S. (2012). The relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(9), 1518-1526.
- Makabe, S., Takagai, J., Asanuma, Y., Ohtomo, K., & Kimura, Y. (2015). Impact of work-life imbalance on job satisfaction and quality of life among hospital nurses in Japan. *Industrial health*, 53(2), 152–159. doi:10.2486/indhealth.2014-0141.
- Malhotra, N., & Mukherjee, A. (2004). The relative influence of organisational commitment and job satisfaction on service quality of customer-contact employees in banking call centres. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 18(3), 162-174.
- McGee, J. E., Peterson, M., Mueller, S. L., & Sequeira, J. M. (2009). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy: Refining the measure. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(4), 965-988.
- Millán, J. M., Hessels, J., Thurik, R., & Aguado, R. (2013). Determinants of job satisfaction: A European comparison of self-employed and paid employees. *Small Business Economics*, 40 (3), 651–670.
- Mitchell, J., & Esnard, T. (2014). Socio-Economic Factors and Job Satisfaction among Public Health Care Registered Nurses in Trinidad and Tobago. *International Journal of Business and Social Research*, 4(6), 27-37. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.18533/ijbsr.v4i6.538
- Morrison, R. (2004). Informal relationships in the workplace: Associations with job satisfaction, organisational commitment and turnover intentions. *New Zealand Journal of Psychology*, 33(3), 114-128.
- Mullins, L., & Christy, G. (2010). *Management and Organisational Behaviour*. Harlow, Essex: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
- Naidu, R.S., Gobin, I., Ashraph, A., Newton, J.T. & Gibbons, D.E. (2002). The working practices and job satisfaction of dental nurses in Trinidad and Tobago: Findings of a national survey. *International Dental Journal*, 52, 321-324.
- Naidu, R., Newton, J. T., & Ayers, K. (2006). A comparison of career satisfaction amongst dental healthcare professionals across three health care systems: comparison of data from the United Kingdom, New Zealand and Trinidad & Tobago. *BMC health services research*, 6, 32. doi:10.1186/1472-6963-6-32.
- Nelson, B. (2005). *1001 Ways to Reward Employees*. New York : Workman Pub.
- Onuoha P., Stephen A., Bernard P., Corban, A., Mahabir, M., & Israel-Richardson, D. (2017). Factors that contribute to work motivation and job satisfaction among hospital nurses in Trinidad and Tobago. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, 7(1), 208-217.
- Ramdwar, Marcus, N.A., Stoute, Valerie A., Ganpat, Wayne G. (2015) - Extension Officers' Perceptions of Farmers' Groups in Trinidad, West Indies and Implications for Extension, *Journal of International Agricultural and Extension Education*, 22 (1), pp35-48. doi:10.5191/jiaee.2015.221TBD

Robbins S. P. (2003). *Organizational behaviour concepts, controversies, application* (8th ed). Prentice-hall International. New Jersey, USA.

Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. (2007). *Organizational behavior*. Upper Saddle River, N.J: Pearson/Prentice Hall.

Saari, M. L., & Judge, A. T. (2004). Employee attitude and job satisfaction. *Human Resource Management, 43*(4), 395-407.

Schermerhorn, J., Hunt, J., & Osborn, R. (2005). *Organizational Behavior* (9th ed.). John Wiley. New York. NY.

Shields, M.A., & Ward, M. (2001). Improving nurse retention in the national health service in England: The impact of job satisfaction on intention to quit. *Journal of Health Economics, 20*, 677-701.

Singh, P., & Loncar, N. (2010). Pay satisfaction, job satisfaction and turnover intent. *Relations Industrielles/Industrial Relations, 65*(3), 470-490. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7202/044892ar>

Snipes, R. L., Oswald, S. L., LaTour, M., & Armenakis, A. A. (2005). The effects of specific job satisfaction facets on customer perceptions of service quality: An employee-level analysis. *Journal of Business Research, 58*, 1330-1339.

Sousa-Poza, A., & Sousa-Poza, A. A. (2000). Well-being at work: A cross-national analysis of the levels and determinants of job satisfaction. *The Journal of Socio-Economics, 29*(6), 517-538. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1053-5357\(00\)00085-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1053-5357(00)00085-8)

Spector, P. (1997). *Job Satisfaction: Application, Assessment, Causes and Consequences*. California: Sage.

Sverke, M., Hellgren, J. & Näswall, K. (2002). No security: A meta analysis and review of job insecurity and its consequences. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, 7*(3): 242–264.

Teck-Hong, T., & Waheed, A. (2011). Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory and job satisfaction in the Malaysian retail sector: The mediating effect of love of money. *Asian Academy of Management Journal, 16*(1), 73-94.

Tessema, M. T., Ready, K. J., & Embaye, A. B. (2013). The Effects of Employee Recognition, Pay, and Benefits on Job Satisfaction: Cross Country Evidence. *Journal of Business and Economics, 4*(1), 1–12.

Weiss, H. M. (2002). Deconstructing job satisfaction: Separating evaluations, beliefs, and affective experiences. *Human Resource Management Review, 12*, 173 – 194.

Wichert, I. C., Nolan, J. P., & Burchell, B. J. (2000) *Workers on the Edge: Job Security, Psychological Well-Being, and Family Life*. Washington, DC: Economic Policy Institute.

Yoon, M., Beatty, S., & Suh, J. (2001). The effect of work climate on critical employee and customer outcomes: An employee-level analysis. *International Journal of Service Industry Management, 12*, 500-521.

Yousef, D. A. (1998). Satisfaction with job security as a predictor of organizational commitment and job performance in a multicultural environment. *International Journal of Manpower, 19*(3), 184-194.

Yusoff, F. W., Kian, S. T., & Idris, M. T. M. (2013). Herzberg's two-factor theory on work motivation: Does it work for today's environment? *Global Journal of Commerce & Management Perspective, 2*(5), 18-22.

